

Arsonophenyl and Sulphonamidophenyl Derivatives of 2-Arylimino 4-Thiazolidone-1-Dioxides

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5-Arsonophenyl and 5-Sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of nine 2-arylimino 4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides have been synthesised for possible use as amoebicides and bactericides respectively.

In view of the pharmacological interest of 1-dioxides of thiazolidones, and encouraging results achieved in our research investigations in this field^{1,2}, it was considered of interest to prepare some 5-arsonophenyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides and of 5-sulphonamidophenyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides as potential amoebicides and bactericides respectively.

2-Arylimino-4-thiazolidones and their -1-dioxides were prepared by the methods of Rout *et al.*³ and Trivedi *et al.*⁴ respectively.

Diazotized arsanilic acid and sulphanilamide were coupled with 2-arylimino 4-thiazolidone -1-dioxides and the resulting azocompounds were decomposed with splitting off of nitrogen. It is assumed that the arsonophenyl or the sulphonamidophenyl group will be attached to the -CH₂-group in 5-position. Previously it has been shown that arsonophenyl or sulphonamidophenyl group is attached to an active methylene group which is in alpha-position to an activating carbonyl group¹⁻². In 4-thiazolidones, the -CH₂-group in the 5-position is in alpha-position to the activating carbonyl group, hence the placement of the arsonophenyl and sulphonamido group in the 5-position is justified.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Arsonophenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxide: *p*-arsanilic acid (1.8 g.) was diazotised and the resulting solution was added slowly with stirring to a solution of 2-phenylimino 4-thiazolidone -1-dioxide (2.4 g.) in acetone alcohol mixture (50 ml.) containing sodium acetate (4.5 g.) at 0-5°. This was followed by dropwise addition of a solution of cupric chloride (3 g.) in water (10 ml.) with stirring during 3 to 4 hrs at 0°. The reaction mixture was warmed on the water-bath (40-50°) for 4 to 5 hrs till the evolution of gas ceased. The buff coloured copper salt was collected, decomposed with 2N sodium hydroxide solution. Cupric hydroxide was removed by filtration and the filtrate was acidified carefully with dilute

1. H. K. Pujari, and M. K. Rout, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 563.
2. A. K. Panigrahi, P. K. Jesthi, and M. K. Rout, *J. and Proc. Inst. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 175.
3. G. N. Mahapatra and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 17.
4. B. K. Raval and J. J. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 195.

acetic acid. The substance which separated out on standing was collected and dried, (m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield—50%). (Found : C, 41.99; H, 2.96; As, 17.53; N, 6.21%; $C_{15}H_{13}N_2SO_6As$, requires C, 42.57; H, 3.07; As, 17.69; N, 6.60%).

Other arsonophenyl derivatives were prepared similarly and their analytical data and m.p. are given in Table I.

TABLE I

5-Arsonophenyl 2-arylimino 4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides

No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Arsenic		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	> 300	50	17.53	17.69	6.21	6.60
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	50	16.29	16.35	5.93	6.10
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	45	16.13	16.35	5.88	6.10
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	55	16.27	16.35	5.98	6.10
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	> 300	60	16.98	17.12	5.99	6.39
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	> 300	55	17.07	17.12	6.03	6.39
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	> 300	50	16.97	17.12	5.92	6.39
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitro phenyl	> 300	50	15.87	15.99	8.54	8.95
9.	alpha-naphthyl	> 300	55	15.78	15.82	5.60	5.90

5-Sulphonamidophenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxide : Sulphanilamide (1 g.) was diazotised and the resulting solution was added slowly with stirring to a solution of 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxide (1 g.) in acetone-alcohol mixture (50 ml.) containing sodium acetate (3 g.) at $0-5^\circ$. A solution of cupric chloride (2 g.) in water (10 ml.) was then added dropwise during 3 to 4 hrs at 0° . The reaction mixture was warmed on the water-bath ($40-50^\circ$) with stirring for 4 to 5 hrs till the evolution of gas ceased. The product which separated out was washed with hot water and finally crystallised from ethanol (m.p. $> 300^\circ$, yield, 65%). (Found : C, 46.84; H, 3.17; S, 16.82; N, 10.94%; $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2O_5$ requires C, 47.5; H, 3.43; S, 16.89; N, 11.09%).

The analytical data, m.p. of sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of other 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

5-Sulphonamidophenyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone-1-dioxides :

No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	> 300	65	10.94	11.09	16.82	16.89
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	60	9.98	10.16	15.39	15.48
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	55	10.11	10.16	15.42	15.48
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	55	9.94	10.16	15.44	15.48
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	> 300	60	10.58	10.69	16.21	16.29
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	> 300	55	10.61	10.69	16.23	16.29
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	> 300	55	10.63	10.69	16.20	16.29
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitro phenyl	> 300	60	13.13	13.20	14.91	15.10
9.	alpha-Naphthyl	> 300	62	9.69	9.78	14.83	14.91

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